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Optimising Sampling Design with Semivariogram for Vegetation Survey of Derived Savannah, Ogun State, Nigeria

Author's Details:

O. B. Banjo^{1*}, D. A. Akintunde-Alo², P. O. Ige²

¹Department of Forestry, Wildlife and Fisheries, Olabisi Onabanjo University, P. M. B. 0012, Ayetoro Campus, Ogun State, Nigeria.

²Department of Social and Environmental Forestry, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: oluseun.banjo@oouagoiwoye.edu.ng; +2348101156580

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Abstract

Vegetation survey is useful for biodiversity conservation and management. Sampling design strategies oftentimes fail to capture the heterogeneous vegetation structure of area being studied due to cost and time constraint. The study aimed to determine the optimum sampling design for vegetation assessment in the study area by characterizing spatial structure and identifying extent of spatial correlation in data points. Hypothetical sampling scenarios of low, medium and high density random and transect sample plots of (3 x 3 km) were laid on Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) from Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) satellite imagery of the study area. NDVI values were extracted for the respective sampling scenarios. Data were subjected to descriptive statistics and fitted to spherical, exponential and Gaussian's semivariogram models. Best fitted models were evaluated by Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values. Nugget, sill and range parameters of the best fitted semivariogram models described the spatial structure of the vegetation cover in the study area. Therefore, the parameter estimates guided the selection of medium density random sample plots and low density transect-laid sample plots as the optimized sampling design most suitable for vegetation survey in derived savannah ecosystem of Ogun State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Vegetation survey; semivariogram models; NDVI; sampling designs; spatial structure

INTRODUCTION

Vegetation survey is a systematic assessment of composition and distribution of plant species within an ecosystem for the purpose of quantifying the structure of the ecosystem with the view to enhancing biodiversity conservation and ecosystem stability (Muhoko *et al.*, 2020; Strohbach *et al.*, 2001). Derived savannah is a vast transitional terrestrial ecosystem situated between lowland rainforest and guinea savanna ecological zones (Akintuyi, *et al.*, 2021; Guy-Casimir *et al.*, 2021), comprising of degraded forest with few scattered trees and regrowth of grasses, occasioned by pervasive anthropogenic activities such as fuelwood harvesting, arable farming and cattle herding (Yilangai *et al.*, 2023).

Spatial heterogeneity continues to characterize the structure of vegetation cover in derived savannah ecosystem owing to vagaries of persistent anthropogenic activities (Rabiou *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the study of large heterogeneous vegetation structure of derived savannah becomes very challenging. Data collection over

expansive ecosystem is usually laborious, costly and time-consuming (Jaakkola *et al.*, 2017). Field survey has been one of the traditional methods of data collection for vegetation survey for many years (Liang *et al.*, 2015). Conventional classical statistics is premised on a crucial assumption of independence of observations, and studies have shown that spatial correlation exists in most ecological processes (Blanchet *et al.*, 2011). However, accurate assessment of vegetation structure of the derived savannah is required for preparing effective conservation and management plans for ecological resources.

The use of remote sensing technology is becoming increasingly useful in ecological study as information over large areas is provided at a relatively low cost (Meresa & Gebrewhid, 2019). Satellite images reveal the spatial, spectral, radiometric and temporal variations in targeted landscape ecosystems. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) has been proven to provide relevant description of chemical composition and physiological growth patterns of plants (Roberts *et al.*, 2012; Burai *et al.*, 2015). One of the widely used vegetation indices for vegetation structure analysis is NDVI which combines ratio of Near Infra-Red (NIR) and Red (R) spectral bands of satellite imageries (Wagenseil *et al.*, 2006).

Ideal sampling designs are statistically sound, simple to apply, economical, produce trustworthy estimates with minimal sampling errors (Stehman, 2001; de Gruijter *et al.*, 2006). Selection of number and sizes of sample plot during field survey are usually chosen arbitrarily without detailed consideration for the spatial variability of the intended object or variable. Sampling strategy is often not optimized to capture enough variability in ecological study in order to obtain valid results from which reasonable conclusions are made.

Heterogeneity of vegetation cover can be characterized by semivariogram model (Silveira *et al.*, 2017). Experimental semi-variogram is assessed against fitted theoretical model with known mathematical features by comparing their parameter estimates to describe spatial structure of vegetation cover (Garrigues *et al.*, 2006). The semivariogram model can be used to optimize sampling design for vegetation study by characterizing spatial structures and identifying the degree and extent of spatial correlation of the data points (Atkinson and Lewis, 2000). Key parameters of modeled semi-variogram are as follows: (a) Range - the distance beyond which data points are no longer spatially correlated. This information is valuable when deciding how to space sample sites effectively. Placing samples further apart than the range value means the data obtained from those points should be statistically independent, reducing spatial redundancy and increasing the efficiency of the sampling plan; (b) Nugget - measure of variability at scales smaller than the minimum distance between data points. A large nugget effect may indicate considerable variability at smaller scales, suggesting that sample points should be placed close together to capture this information; and (c) Sill which describes the total spatial variability. If the sill is high, it means that there's a high variation, and thus more samples may be required to capture this variability.

In this study, pixel value of NDVI was considered as realization of regionalized variable, describing the spatial distribution of aspects of vegetation cover in the satellite imagery. The empirical variogram examined the relationship between distance and pairs of pixels to describe the spatial variation of vegetation structure of derived savannah ecosystem of Ogun State. Semi-variogram parameters of the spatial structure from hypothetical sampling scenarios of low, medium and high density Temporary Sample Plots (TSP) arranged on random and/or transect line placement were assessed and compared. This provided the guidance on the number and arrangement of samples needed to effectively capture the spatial variability in vegetation assessment. Therefore, the study assessed optimized sampling strategies with semivariogram models to effectively capture the spatial heterogeneity of Derived Savannah Ecosystem of Ogun State.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The study area was the Derived Savannah region of Ogun State situated between latitude 6° 32' 00" and 7° 43' 05"N and longitude 2° 44' 00"E and 3° 4' 30"E in the southwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria (Sanusi *et al.*, 2013), covering approximately 9382.51 km² (Figure 1).

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Figure 1: Derived Savannah region of Ogun State, Nigeria

Annual rainfall is between 100mm and 200mm from April to November with a bi-modal peak pattern in May-June and September-October. Rains drain into Yewa River which runs from North to South with its tributaries as Rivers Oyan and Oba with average maximum daily temperature of 28°C and 32°C in wet and dry seasons respectively (Adepitan et al., 2017; Adedeji *et al.*, 2014; Oluwalana, 1997). The average relative humidity is generally high, usually above 80% during the rainy seasons, and ranges between 60% and 80% in the dry season. The geology of the study area is characterized by basement complex rocks of the pre-cambian origin which form the overlying sedimentary layer consisting of cretaceous, tertiary and quaternary sediments deposited in the coastal plains and culminating in soils that are mostly lateritic and sandy varying in components and texture (OGMF, 2004). The topography is undulating with small hills at elevations between 15m and 70m above sea level and lowland terrain which slopes in the north-south direction resulting in the southward flow of majority of the rivers that transverse the State (Ogundele *et al.*, 2013). The woodland vegetation is characterized by varying types of woody species that include: *Hymenocardia acida*, *Anogeissus leiocarpus*, *Lophira lanceolata*, *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides*, *Cassia siamea*, *Isobertinia doka*, *Uapaca togoensis*, *Bridelia ferruginea*, *Daniellia oliveri*.

Data acquisition and processing

Landsat imagery has been identified to possess relatively high resolution data and have been proven suitable for vegetation analysis (Lemenkova, 2015). Landsat 8 OLI imagery (30 m spatial resolution) was used to effectively capture the spatial heterogeneity. The image dataset was acquired in January 2019 (minimal cloud cover) from the United States Geological Survey for Earth Observation and Science (USGS/EOS). Distortions in the imagery had been geometrically rectified and the NDVI data was calculated directly from the reflectance values in the near-infrared (NIR) band and the visible red band (RED) of image data for each pixel.

Sampling design scenarios

Hypothetical sampling designs of 3 x 3 km Temporary Sample Plots (TSP) were simulated at high, medium and low densities across the study area as follows (Figure 2): (a) 50 Random TSP (b) 250 Random TSP (c) 450 random TSP (d) 95 transect-laid TSP (e) 53 transect-laid TSP (f) 28 transect-laid TSP. NDVI readings were obtained for the 6 sets of sampling design scenarios by extracting the NDVI pixel values to the different sampling positions using the extraction tool in ArcGIS.

Figure 2 (a-f): Hypothetical sampling scenarios

Data analysis

Data exploration was performed to assess the spatial correlation of data for possible transformation. Data were subjected to descriptive statistics and regression-kriging analysis in geostatistics by fitting the data to experimental semivariogram models that included spherical, Gaussian’s and exponential models in Table 1, with parameters shown in Figure 3. Model for each scenario was assessed using the RMSE, such that, the model with the least RMSE was adjudged most suitable. Statistical analysis was performed in R (R CoreTeam, 2016) while spatial regression-kriging analysis was done using ArcGIS 10.3 (Allen, 2016).

Table 1: Experimental semi-variogram models

Model	Formula
Spherical	$\gamma(h) = \sigma^2 \left(\frac{3h}{2\phi} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{h}{\phi} \right)^3 \right)$
Gaussian’s	$\gamma(h) = \sigma^2 \left(1 - e^{-3\left(\frac{h}{\phi}\right)^2} \right)$
Exponential	$\gamma(h) = \sigma^2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{3h}{\phi}} \right)$

Semi-variance $\gamma(h)$, sill (σ^2), range (ϕ), distance (h), and exponent (e)

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Figure 3: Graph of semivariogram model - $\gamma(h)$ = Semi-variance sill (σ^2), range (ϕ), distance, h and nugget effect (τ^2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics

Summary statistics of the NDVI for the respective sampling scenarios are presented in Table 2. Average NDVI values for low, medium and high random sampling scenarios were 0.286, 0.297 and 0.293 respectively while the mean NDVI values for low, medium and high density transect-laid TSP were 0.301, 0.294 and 0.290 respectively. The NDVI values among the sampling scenarios were not significantly different ($F_{5,853} = 0.859$; $p = 0.508$) from one another as shown in Figure 4. This result implies that there was evidence of spatial autocorrelation in the NDVI data such that their spatial dependency can be modeled using semi-variogram (Woodcock *et al.*, 1988).

Table 2: Summary statistics of NDVI values of sampling scenarios

Sampling Scenarios	NDVI			
	Min	Max	Mean	SD
50 Random TSP	0.247	0.365	0.286	0.084
250 Random TSP	0.235	0.581	0.297	0.046
450 Random TSP	0.223	0.449	0.293	0.035
14km-Interval Transect	0.267	0.444	0.301	0.037
28km-Interval Transect	0.235	0.414	0.294	0.040
42km-Interval Transect	0.235	0.444	0.290	0.040

Min = Minimum; Max = Maximum; SD = Standard Deviation; TSP = Temporary Sample Plot

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Figure 4: Mean difference of NDVI values of sampling scenarios

Semivariogram curves

Semivariogram of the sampling scenarios provided distinct curves showing the parameter estimates for random TSP (Figure 5) and transect-laid TSP (Figure 6) that quantified the spatial structure of vegetation cover of the study area using NDVI values (Wallace *et al.*, 2000).

Figure 5: Semivariogram curves for systematic random TSP

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Figure 6: Semivariogram curves for transect-laid TSP

According to Table 3 and Table 4, models with lowest RMSE value were selected as the best fitted models. Gaussian's model was best-fitted for the low density sampling scenarios in both systematic random TSP and transect-laid TSP while exponential and spherical models were best suited for medium and high density sampling scenarios in random and transect TSP respectively.

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Table 3: Parameter estimates of systematic random sampling scenarios

Parameters	50 Random TSP (LD)			250 Random TSP (MD)			450 Random TSP (HD)		
	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's
Nugget	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000553	0.000253	0.000000	0.0000505	0.0001938	0.0000792	0.00034
Sill	0.000868	0.000979	0.0008151	0.001651	0.002016	0.0013760	0.0000960	0.001182	0.00820
Range	51015.14	91224.43	39677.14	39544.21	48848.14	32013.12	35364.04	47934.22	30478.11
RMSE	0.0126	0.0127	0.0120*	0.0206	0.0200*	0.0218	0.0181	0.0177*	0.0199

TSP = Temporary Sample Plot; LD = Low Density; MD = Medium Density; HD = High Density; (*) = Selected Model

Table 4: Parameter estimates of transect sampling scenarios

Parameters	14km Transect TSP (HD)			28km Transect TSP (MD)			42km Transect TSP (LD)		
	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's	Spherical	Exponential	Gaussian's
Nugget	0.000615	0.000249	0.000751	0.000182	0.00000	0.000386	0.000207	0.00000	0.000435
Sill	0.000685	0.000106	0.000552	0.001040	0.00130	0.000839	0.00114	0.00147	0.000939
Range	0.2503	0.21659	0.22219	0.24548	0.30996	0.21665	0.29867	0.38535	0.27518
RMSE	0.0399*	0.0409	0.0408	0.0275*	0.0277	0.0279	0.028984	0.02916	0.028978*

TSP = Temporary Sample Plot; LD = Low Density; MD = Medium Density; HD = High Density; (*) = Selected Model

Semivariogram parameter estimates

Sill parameter estimate was highest for MD systematic random sampling, followed by HD and LD. The sill estimate was also highest for MD transect-laid sampling scenario, followed by HD and LD. For relatively high sill semivariogram estimates, substantial numbers of samples are required to optimally capture spatial variation in vegetation structure (Biswas *et al.*, 2013). The sill parameter estimates from the best-fitted semivariogram models expressed evidence of high spatial variation in the NDVI values which were most suited to medium density sampling scenarios in both systematic random and transect TSP placements.

Nugget parameter estimate expresses the amount of small scale variability observed in minimum distance between two NDVI values, thus implying that relatively high nugget value indicate closer placement of sampling points than the minimum distance for spatial variability to be captured (Van Groenigen, 2000). Relatively low nugget effects were observed in this study for all the sampling scenarios. However, nugget effects were most minimal in medium density TSP placements for both systematic random and transect sampling scenarios.

Range parameter estimates describe the maximum distance between sampling points beyond which spatial data are statistically independent (Pardo-Iguzquiza and Dowd, 2013). The range estimates of best-fitted semivariogram models in this study were highest for MD systematic random TSP followed by HD and LD. However, LD had the highest range value in transect-laid TSP, followed by HD and MD. The range estimates imply that optimum sampling design requires placement of TSP at observed maximum range between sampling points in order to ensure independence of observation of NDVI values.

CONCLUSION

Semivariogram models were used to analyse spatial structure of vegetation cover in derived savannah ecosystem of Ogun State, Nigeria for the purpose of optimising sampling designs for effective vegetation assessment. Hypothetical sampling scenarios of low, medium and high density random and transect sample plots were created on NDVI derived from Landsat 8 OLI imagery of the study area. The degree and extent of spatial correlation of NDVI values were evaluated for the respective sampling scenarios.

The study revealed evidence of spatial autocorrelation of NDVI values among the sampling scenario as these values were not significantly different from one another, thus validating the use of semivariogram to model the spatial structure of the vegetation cover. Semivariogram curves of the sampling scenarios distinctly showed that spatial structures of vegetation cover from which parameter estimates were extracted.

The nugget, sill and range parameter estimates under the medium density random sampling and low density transect scenarios were observed to most suitably capture the spatial heterogeneity of the derived savannah ecosystem of Ogun State. Therefore, medium density random sample plots and low density transect-laid sample plots appeared to be best sampling designs for vegetation assessment in the study area.

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